

مفتاح التفسير

also known as “Key to Qur'an Interpretation”, “Miftah at-Tafsir”

By Assoc Prof Jabir Musa Suleiman, Federal University Dutsin-Ma Katsina Nigeria

Entry tags: Qur'anic commentary (Tafsir), Uthmaniyyah, Religious Group, Qur'anic science, Text, Islamic Traditions, Islamic Revival

The book was designed as a guide on the basic knowledge of interpreting the Holy Qur'an.

Date Range: 1766 CE - 1828 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim
[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Fodio, A. (Nd.). Miftahu al-Tafsir. Maktabatu Makhtutat.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/3939fc58cb7516f4ef4616a43191848fa765cc25/23319f0e4367827a0b7ef1d21260c

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://siiasi.org/digital-archive/shaykh-abdullahi-ibn-fuduye/>

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

- ↳ Tomb
– No
- ↳ Cemetery
– No
- ↳ Temple
– No
- ↳ Shrine
– No
- ↳ Altar
– Yes
- ↳ Devotional marker
– No
- ↳ Cenotaph
– No
- ↳ Church
– No
- ↳ Mosque
– Yes
- ↳ Synagogue
– No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
– No
- ↳ Monument
– No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
– No

- ↳ Cave(s)
 - No
- ↳ Hilltops
 - No
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - No
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - No
- ↳ Domestic contexts
 - Yes
- ↳ Library/archive
 - Yes
- ↳ Specify
 - Specify: Homes For Personal uses

Methods of Composition

- Incised or Inscribed

Notes: The text was inscribed on brown paper with an ink

- ↳ Method of inscription
 - Other [specify]: Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Paper

Notes: A scanned copy of the paper on which the text was inscribed.

- ↳ Specify type of paper
 - Specify: Brown Paper

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- No

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

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–Other [specify]: Ink

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Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?
– No

– Yes

Notes: The production of the text remained under the polity for the position of the author as the leader of the caliphate.

↳ Are the authors/copyists/engravers paid by the polity?
– Yes
Notes: But the position of the author as caliph made the funding indirectly.

↳ Does the polity provide financial support to religious infrastructure involved with textual production?
– Yes
Notes: The polity supported text production by establishing schools to educate people on the

book's content.

↳ Are the leaders of the polity and the religion the same figure?

– Yes

↳ Are political officials involved in the support of textual production?

– Yes

Notes: The author and many other officials supported the textual production of the book.

↳ Are political officials and religious officials otherwise overlapping institutional networks?

– Yes

Notes: Political and Religious support each other for the transformation of the caliphate.

↳ Does the polity enforce religious observance according to text or texts?

– Yes

Notes: Observance of Religious services according to the prescription of the text remained mandatory within the caliphate.

↳ Is the polity legal code derived from religious text(s) in question?

– No

↳ Is preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax exemption) present in the polity to support the text(s)...

– No

↳ Are religious specialists present/in charge of the production of the text or copies of the text?

– Yes

↳ Present full-time?

– No

↳ Present part-time?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific sex/gender?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific ethnicity?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of a specific class/caste?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists dedicated to the place for life?

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for living spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there regulations/provisions for training spaces of religious specialists?

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of a body of religious specialists?

– No

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

–Total audience: 500000000

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (estimated population, numerical)

–Number: 5000000

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience

–smallest audience: 1000000

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience

–largest audience: 10000000

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size

–Specify: Birth Rate and Increase in population

↳ Number of audience within the sample region (% of sample region population, numerical)

– Number: 70

↳ What is the size of the smallest known audience
– smallest audience: 10

↳ What is the size of the largest known audience
– largest audience: 70

↳ What factors might account for historical changes in audience size
– Specify: Increase or decrease in population

↳ Nature of audience
[select all that apply]

- Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)
- Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)
- Small religious group (trying to be organized-controlled by larger religious group)
- Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

↳ Can scholarly and emic notions of the audience differ?
– No

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– Yes

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Production

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Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

- No

Is there material significance to the text?

- No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

- Yes

Notes: The Spirit body of Angels was described in the text.

Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

- Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

- Yes

Other spirit-body relationship?

- Yes

Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– No

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– No

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– Yes

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The creator is ever watchful of human activities

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– Yes

↳ Food

– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s)

– No

↳ Sacred object(s)

– No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex
– No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery
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– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?
– Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about other
– Specify: Yes

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Vocabulary

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: A series of issues associated with the afterlife was described by the text, such as judgment, paradise, and Hellfire.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world?

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space?

– No

↳ Afterlife in "other" space?

– Yes

Notes: At a space only known to Allah

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

↳ Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text discussed some issues related to eschatology such as life after death, judgment, etc

- ↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime
 - No
- ↳ At specified time in future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in near future
 - No
- ↳ At unspecified time in distant future
 - No
- ↳ At some other time [specify]
 - Yes
 - Notes: Not specified, only known to Allah
- ↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end
 - No
- ↳ Divine judgment event
 - Yes
- ↳ Restoration of the world
 - No
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle
 - Yes
 - Notes: It discussed temporal life inside the grave
- ↳ Establishment of new political system
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of new religious system
 - No
- ↳ Other form of eschatology?
 - Specify: Questioning inside the grave

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– No

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Notes: It expresses science for the interpretation of the Qur'an

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Notes: The Text is a single book

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– Yes

Notes: He bestowes reward

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– Yes

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings
 - No
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms?
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of extreme sensory pleasure?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of eternal happiness?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation as a superior life form?
 - No
 - ↳ Consists of reincarnation in a superior realm?
 - No

↳ Other?
– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime?
– No
Notes: Is only bestowed in the afterlife

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity
– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)
– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)
– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence
– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance
– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity
– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving
– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude
– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity
– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

↳ Optimism/hope

– Yes

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– Yes

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– I don't know

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Science of Qur'an

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Incomprehensible?

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Notes: The text guide for Qur'an Interpretation alone

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

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↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

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Beliefs

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Notes: The Spirit body of Angels was described in the text.

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The creator is ever watchful of human activities

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular
– Yes

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?
– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos
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Notes: He bestowes reward

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– No

Notes: Is only bestowed in the afterlife

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text discussed some issues related to eschatology such as life after death, judgment, etc

↳ Eschaton is in this lifetime

– No

↳ At specified time in future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ At unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ At some other time [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Not specified, only known to Allah

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end

– No

↳ Divine judgment event

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world

– No

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle

– Yes

Notes: It discussed temporal life inside the grave

↳ Establishment of new political system

– No

↳ Establishment of new religious system

– No

↳ Other form of eschatology?

– Specify: Questioning inside the grave

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

↳ Moderation/frugality

– Yes

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical)
– Yes
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
– Yes
- ↳ Humility/modesty
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism/hope
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
– I don't know
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
– Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
– Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
– Yes

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

↳ Other important virtues

– Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy permanently?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate bureaucracy temporarily/seasonally?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group?

– No

↳ Does the text dictate how individuals interact with other institutional bureaucracies?

– Yes

↳ Does the text regulate the primary supporting income of the place?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: Caliphate

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mention food production/disbursement?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: But was indirectly

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text specified some schools of Law such as that of Maliki, Shafi'i, Hanafi, Ash'ari etc

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Notes: No, the text does not restrict any form of religious education

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: Caliphate

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– An empire

Notes: But was indirectly

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– Other

Notes: No

Welfare

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↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out land?

– No

↳ Does the text provide for provisions to lease out tools?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

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